

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES (ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN) TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: *The development, prospects, prosperity, spiritual growth of a state and society, its place among the most developed countries in the world depend on educated, high intellectual potential, young people who have good qualities in their hearts and minds, mature and well-rounded in all respects. It is an honorable and at the same time responsible task for teachers and educators to bring up a selfless, faithful generation that will serve the destiny of the motherland, to raise teaching to a higher level in terms of quality and content.*

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At present, not only students of schools, lyceums and universities, but also MTM students and employees working in various fields are taught foreign languages, in particular, English. There is a reason for this, of course. The study of the languages of economically, scientifically and culturally developed countries is a key factor in achieving the achievements of world science and development.

In preschools, classes should be held twice a week for 20-25 minutes. Of course, this process requires great strength, knowledge and skill from the teacher. Because children do not know how to write at this age, they receive all the information through the sense of sight and hearing. As a result, the learning process takes the form of oral speech. Effective use of additional resources in teaching English to children, increasing their interest and attitude to English with the help of visual aids, conducting lessons in an interactive way, engaging students in additional lessons and in this process 'The use of traditional methods gives good results. According to experts, a child will be physiologically ready to learn a second language at the age of 6-7. But during this period it is enough to develop the ability to think logically and creatively through educational games, to remember the names of toys, animals, household items and similar small details using moving materials. In order to make English lessons more interesting in MTCs, a textbook called

“English in pictures” was created on the basis of the program “Let's make friends with English”. The book is intended for children from 5 to 7 years old. ”, “My Home”.

English teachers of preschool age make full use of the objects around them, cards and other textbooks, using simple methods of teaching. When teaching words like banana and apple, teachers can also teach new words that suddenly express color by pointing to fruits such as bananas and apples. Children are taught to use a foreign language through the objects in the room to organize lessons. Of course, the methodology of teachers plays an important role in the use of materials in teaching. For example, when teaching appropriate words, you first show the object to the child and encourage him to speak, students pronounce the words and repeat the new word again using the pictures on the cards to reinforce the word they pronounced. is pronounced. When teaching words, teachers will be able to determine the content of the text and the educator will be able to draw the students' attention by saying the words and drawing a picture on the board to get their attention. The introduction of new pedagogical technologies in the English language education system, their application, the use of interesting methods are bearing fruit. Modern pedagogical technologies are now becoming a necessary and essential component of the educational process for preschool education. The need to use advanced pedagogical technologies in the formation of English as a tool of communication in preschool education shows the effectiveness of interactive methods, the importance of acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills. Motivation of education plays an important role in the organization of educational activities. It stimulates thinking, critical observation, and increases the richness of the English vocabulary. A powerful motivating factor is the activation of children's interests and abilities in teaching English in preschool institutions, the methods of education that meet their needs in learning new material.

Language learning also depends on age. According to psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. The natural tendency of children to learn a language, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children spend more time than adults are the main reasons for this. It should be noted that children aged 6-7 years do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, teaching English to primary school students should not start with giving them a grammatical understanding. Otherwise, from the

very first step of teaching a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest.

Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is much more difficult and responsible. The following methods can be used to teach children meaningful and interesting English:

- riddles; Children have a strong interest in finding answers to riddles. Therefore, even if the teacher says the riddle in English or Uzbek, he should ask the children to answer it in English. Then children learn words quickly.

- Practical exercises (tasting fruits and other foods, smelling flowers); This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "An educator who wants something to be firmly entrenched in the children's memory should use as many of the child's senses as possible in the eyes, ears, sound organ, muscle senses, and even if possible, try to involve the sense of smell and taste in the process of remembering." For example, when a teacher tastes an apple, the color is red or green. He should inform the students about the sweet (tasty) or sour (), fragrant () smell, and feed the other students the fruit, and ask them to give the children information in English about that fruit. When the teacher asks the students the English name of the colors, the child immediately remembers when he ate the fruit, quickly remembers that it is red-red, green-green. Lumot in long-term memory ensures that it stays in place.

- through gestures, facial expressions; When a teacher speaks or gives a command to a child, for example, if the child uses gestures such as come here, open the book, stand up, look at the board (look at the blackboard) will be clear.

- through visual aids, posters, books;

- things that are visible and often used in everyday life

Write For example: door, book, table, blackboard, window and so on. Because such objects are always visible and used a lot in practice, the child learns these words involuntarily.

- through news; We know kids are curious. They quickly get bored of the monotony. i Therefore, they should not always be taught using the same methods, but should be taught by changing such methods and updating them. Otherwise, the children will understand what the teacher is teaching and will be prepared for it. Teaching by updating methods will increase children's aspirations.

CONCLUSION

In short, teaching language to young children is not an obligation, but a fun activity, and teaching using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. The importance of learning foreign languages should be properly explained to children through natural conditions. This opportunity gave him the opportunity to study world science and do great things. After all, as our ancestor Navoi said, "He who knows the language knows the hand."

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